

Major *LalbFTa1* gene indels:

LD37 deletion, 635 bp
LD37 inversion, 64 bp
LD37 deletion, 106 bp
LD37 insertion, 1310 bp
LD37 insertion, 59 bp
LD37 deletion, 90 bp
LD37 insertion, 8 bp
P27174 deletion, 687 bp

Major *LalbFTa2* gene indels:

Clovis deletion, 28 bp
GR38 insertion, 246 bp
GR38 insertion, 17 bp
GR38 insertion, 9 bp
GR38 deletion, 46 bp
GR38 deletion, 6 bp
GR38 insertion, 15 bp
GR38 deletion, 4 bp
GR38 insertion, 13 bp
GR38 insertion, 5 bp
GR38 insertion, 74 bp
Clovis insertion, 24 bp

Major *LalbFTc1* gene indels:

GR38 insertion, 8bp
P27174 deletion, 2126 bp
LD37 deletion, 2388 bp
GR38 insertion, 7 bp
LD37 insertion, 24 bp
LD37 deletion, 75 bp
GR38 deletion, 24 bp
LAP022E insertion, 25 bp
LAP022E deletion, 264 bp
LAP022E deletion, 5 bp
LD37 insertion, 3877 bp
P27174 insertion, 3818 bp
GR38 insertion, 3800 bp
LD37 deletion, 4 bp
LAP029B deletion, 7 bp
LAP029B deletion, 28 bp
GR38 deletion, 16 bp

Major *LalbFTc2* gene indels:

GRC5262B indel, 209 bp
Dieta insertion, 13 bp
Dieta deletion, 1463 bp
Dieta deletion, 8 bp

